

Influence of Artificial Intelligence Enhanced Advertisements on the buying Behaviour of Academic Staff of Select Tertiary Institutions in Benin City

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine the influence of artificial intelligence enhanced advertisements on the buying behaviour of academic staff of select tertiary institutions in Benin City. The objectives of this study were to determine the knowledge level of artificial intelligence enhanced advertisements among select academics in Benin City, find out the level of awareness of select academics in Benin of the use of artificial intelligence (AI) enhanced advertisement messages in marketing communications, find out how select academics perceive the effectiveness of artificial intelligence (AI) enhanced advertisement messages and to find out the impact of artificial intelligence (AI) enhanced Advertising messages on the select academics' buying behaviour. The researcher employed survey research design, adopting questionnaire as the instrument of data collection. The findings showed that showed that the respondents are fully aware of the use of artificial intelligence in the enhancement of advertising creation. A significant portion of academics expressed agreement with the perception level of artificial intelligence in enhancing advertisements (49.3%), others expressed nuanced views and dissatisfactions (23.4%), giving room to much more divergence that calls for much more analysis. The findings further showed that artificial intelligence-generated messages have positive impact on buying behaviour. Based on the findings, it was concluded that artificial intelligence is a critical tool of persuasive communication in recent times to engendering behavioural change communication. Thus, academics should make concerted efforts to be aware of the presence of artificial intelligence.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Advertisements, Buying Behaviour, Academic Staff, Tertiary Institutions, Benin City

Introduction

The proliferation of artificial intelligence (AI) and its associated tools in the twenty-first century has brought about systemic disruption to the integrated marketing communication space. The entire gamut of marketing communications, ranging from research, creation and delivery of marketing related messages, have been co-opted into and are being controlled to a very large extent by artificial intelligence (AI), given the exponential growth in technology and as the world system continues to shrink into the embrace of e-commerce, controlled by emerging technological advancements, of which the artificial intelligence is prominent (Gao, Kim & Hussain, 2021). By usage, artificial intelligence has become synonymous with digital natives especially the generation Z, to mean the array of systems, orchestrated by computers that are capable of performing complex tasks that could only be done by human before now, tasks like reasoning, solving problems and making decisions (Copeland, 2019).

Advertisements are very critical to the economy of any nation, given the fact that, they serve as the channel of information about goods, services and other developmental